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Environmental Sustainability at a Global Level

Between 2013 and 2022, it decreased by an average of 7.44%.

The Global Innovation Index (GII) is an index that measures a country's capacity for innovation through a series of key indicators. One of the aspects evaluated by the GII is ecological sustainability, which considers how a country's innovations contribute to environmental sustainability. This parameter includes indicators related to resource efficiency, measuring the efficient use of natural resources such as energy, water, and materials in a country's economy. It also assesses the environmental impact of economic activities, including pollution levels and greenhouse gas emissions. Furthermore, it analyzes the creation and adoption of technologies and practices that promote environmental sustainability, such as renewable energies, sustainable transportation, and organic farming. It considers the presence and effectiveness of environmental policies and regulations aimed at promoting sustainability and evaluates the level of awareness and commitment of the population and businesses towards environmental sustainability. The GII takes these factors into account to provide a comprehensive view of how a country is integrating ecological sustainability into its innovation practices, contributing to a more sustainable and resilient future. The data is available from 2013 to 2022.

Source: Global Innovation Index

Link: <https://prosperitydata360.worldbank.org/en/indicator/WIPO+GII+70>

Global Ecological Sustainability in 2022. The analysis of environmental sustainability data for 2022 reveals a varied landscape among the evaluated countries. Malta ranks at the top with a score of 57.3, closely followed by Ireland with 56.6 and Hong Kong SAR, China with 56.3. These results indicate strong performance in terms of environmental sustainability, suggesting that these nations have implemented effective green policies and practices. Malta, for instance, may have benefited from its island position and policies aimed at conserving natural resources. Ireland, on the other hand, might have made significant progress in renewable energy and waste management, while Hong Kong, despite its urban challenges, could have adopted innovative measures to reduce pollution and improve energy efficiency. Switzerland, with a score of 54, continues to demonstrate its commitment to sustainability, a distinctive feature of its environmental policy for years. Countries like Croatia and Romania, with scores of 52.4 and 52.1 respectively, reflect a balance between economic development and environmental conservation, followed by Bosnia and Herzegovina (51.2) and North Macedonia (50.9), which also show a good level of attention to sustainability. The case of Scandinavian countries like Denmark, which scores 50.7, is interesting as it suggests that despite often being seen as leaders in sustainability, there can be areas for improvement. This could reflect recent challenges or the need

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to update some policies to address new environmental issues. The United Kingdom and Slovakia, both with 50.3, demonstrate substantial commitment but also potential areas for growth. Italy, with a score of 48.7, and Spain, with 47.5, indicate that while significant progress has been made, there is still a way to go to reach the levels of European sustainability leaders. The presence of countries like Serbia (47.5) and the Czech Republic (47.3) in the same range underscores a common commitment in Central and Eastern Europe towards more sustainable practices. Baltic nations like Lithuania (46.9) and Estonia (49.2) show increasing attention to sustainability, indicating a positive change in their environmental policies. However, traditionally progressive countries like Sweden (44.6) and Finland (43.7) score lower than expected, suggesting the need for further analysis to understand the specific challenges they currently face. Moving down the rankings, countries like Japan (37.8), France (36.4), and Germany (38.6) show that even advanced economies have significant room for improvement in terms of environmental sustainability. These scores may reflect difficulties in balancing economic growth with sustainable practices or delays in implementing new green technologies. In the United States, with a score of 25.4, the result indicates a clear need for improvement, especially considering its global environmental impact. Similarly, Middle Eastern countries like Saudi Arabia (19.2) and the United Arab Emirates (34.8) reflect unique challenges related to their oil-based economies and water resource management in arid regions. In the context of emerging and developing economies, countries like China (28.9) and India (16.7) show results that highlight both progress and immense challenges in balancing rapid industrial development and environmental sustainability. China, despite its massive investment in renewable energy, continues to struggle with air pollution and waste management issues. India, on the other hand, faces similar challenges, accentuated by a rapidly growing population and urbanization. Other countries like Brazil (25.3) and Russia (16.1) illustrate the difficulties of large emerging economies in pursuing sustainable growth. These countries must address deforestation, resource extraction, and other practices that can undermine long-term sustainability efforts. The situation in many African countries, such as Nigeria (14.3) and Ethiopia (14), highlights the severe challenges they face in terms of infrastructure and the capacity to implement effective environmental policies. Often, the immediate priority of these countries is economic development and poverty reduction, which can push environmental sustainability to a secondary objective. In conclusion, the 2022 environmental sustainability data shows a wide range of outcomes among countries, reflecting a complexity of factors that include government policies, economic conditions, public awareness, and geographical challenges. While some countries emerge as leaders in sustainability, others highlight critical areas for improvement. This global landscape underscores the importance of customized and sustained strategies to address the specific needs and challenges of each country, promoting a more sustainable future for all.

Environmental Sustainability at a Global Level from 2013 to 2022. Analyzing environmental sustainability data from 2013 to 2022 reveals a diverse landscape among various countries, with some nations showing significant progress and others seeing a decline in their performance. Starting with nations that have shown remarkable improvements, Burkina Faso, although starting from a very low value of 0.2 in 2013, recorded an impressive increase, reaching 18.5 in 2022, with an extraordinary percentage increase of 9150%. This result could be attributed to aggressive environmental policies or targeted international initiatives. Similarly, Niger saw growth from 1.2 to 19.7, representing a percentage increase of 1541.67%, indicating a significant commitment to sustainability. Guinea also showed exceptional improvement, rising from 0.6 to 16.1, with an increase of 2583.33%, and Uganda recorded a growth of 715%, from 2 to 16.3. These countries, many of which are developing, are evidently benefiting from sustainability initiatives and international aid. Other countries like Malta, which rose from 37.8 to 57.3 with an increase of 51.59%, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, which saw an increase of 68.42% from 30.4 to 51.2, have demonstrated significant progress, although starting

from already higher values compared to the previously mentioned countries. Montenegro and North Macedonia have shown similar improvements, with increases of 63.55% and 40.61% respectively. These increases indicate a positive trend towards more sustainable practices, likely due to favorable government policies and the implementation of greener technologies. However, not all countries have shown progress. Some nations have even seen significant declines. Italy, for example, dropped from 67.1 to 48.7, with a decrease of 27.42%. Similarly, Spain recorded a decline of 26.81%, dropping from 64.9 to 47.5. Sweden also saw a worrying decrease, from 59.8 to 44.6, and the Czech Republic, from 63.7 to 47.3. These figures could reflect structural problems, a lack of investment in sustainable technologies, or a shift in political priorities. South Korea recorded one of the worst performances, dropping from 44.8 to 26.8, with a decrease of 40.18%, signaling potential significant challenges in addressing environmental issues. Even some of the world's major economies have seen declines. The United States, for example, dropped from 28.6 to 25.4, with a decrease of 11.19%. Germany, from 41.4 to 38.6, recorded a decrease of 6.76%, while France saw a decline of 16.70%, dropping from 43.7 to 36.4. These figures are particularly concerning given the influential role these countries have in global politics and economics. The decline could be attributed to a range of factors, including political, economic, and social changes that have influenced the focus and resources dedicated to environmental sustainability. Additionally, some countries have seen less drastic but still significant changes. Norway, for example, dropped from 42.7 to 38.2, with a decrease of 10.54%, while Belgium saw a reduction of 9.09%, from 35.2 to 32. The Netherlands also recorded a decrease of 5.74% from 40.1 to 37.8, and Finland, with a decline of 1.13% from 44.2 to 43.7, showed negative trends. In summary, the data shows a great variability in environmental sustainability performance among countries over the considered period. While some countries, especially developing ones, have made remarkable progress, others, including some of the major global players, have seen worrying declines. These results highlight the need for ongoing and strengthened commitment to sustainable policies and practices to address global environmental challenges.

Conclusions. Environmental sustainability measured within the Global Innovation Index framework shows a decreasing trend between 2013 and 2022, with an average reduction of 7.44%. Some countries have shown a high level of growth in environmental sustainability, such as Burkina Faso with a value of 9150.00%, Mali with 5333.33%, Guinea with 2583.33%, Madagascar with 2066.67%, and Niger with 1541.67%. However, there are countries that show a declining level of environmental sustainability compared to the average, such as Tajikistan with -39.01%, North Korea with -40.18%, Nepal with -41.39%, Togo with -49.47%, and Benin with -52.15%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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